

Data Generation Algorithm

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Algorithm 1: Generate test results with 4 possible outcomes

Data: $P_{flaky_tests}, P_{faulty_tests}, N_{tests}, N_{versions}$
Result: Artificial results with seeded flakiness.

```
tests ← generate_tests( $N_{tests}$ );
versions ← generate_versions( $N_{versions}$ );
flaky_tests ← random.choice( $P_{flaky\_tests}, tests$ );
faulty_tests ← random.choice( $P_{faulty\_tests}, tests$ );
flaky_tests ← split into subsets for different number of outcomes and behaviours;
tests ← assign initial probabilities for test  $p_{fault}$  and  $p_{flake}$ ;
version_samples ←  $\emptyset$ ;
foreach  $t$  in tests do
     $\delta$  ← compute_p_flake_update( $t.beaviour, t.p_{flake}$ );
    foreach  $v$  in versions do
         $vs$  ← {};
         $vs.tid$  ←  $t.id$ ;
         $vs.vid$  ←  $v.id$ ;
         $vs.is_faulty$  ← sample binomial( $t.p_{fault}$ );
         $vs.verdict$  ← resolve  $vs.is_faulty$  to Pass or Fail;
         $vs.p_{flake}$  ← update_p_flake( $t.beaviour, t.p_{flake}, \delta$ );
         $vs.possible\_test\_outcomes$  ← assign outcomes for  $v$  based on
             $t.number\_extra\_outcomes$  and  $vs.verdict$ ;
        version_samples.append( $vs$ );
    end
end
result_history ←  $\emptyset$ ;
foreach  $t$  in tests do
    foreach  $v$  in versions do
        runs_recorded ←  $\emptyset$ ;
        run_time ←  $v.start\_time$ ;
         $vs$  ← version_samples[ $(t.id, v.id)$ ];
        foreach  $r$  in  $v.runs$  do
            run_verdict ←  $vs.verdict$ ;
            is_flaky ← sample binomial( $vs.p_{flake}$ );
            if is_flaky then
                run_verdict ←
                    flip_result(run_verdict,  $vs.possible\_test\_outcomes$ , runs_recorded);
            end
            runs_recorded.append( $(r, run\_verdict)$ );
            result ← Create a record with  $t.id, v.id, run\_time$  and  $run\_verdict$ ;
            result_history.append(result);
            update(run_time);
        end
    end
end
```
